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ISSUES OF ANTROPOCENTRIC STUDY OF MODERN LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

The article represents the anthropocentric paradigm that mainly focuses on cognitive linguistics and linguaculturology. There is also analyzed the concept as a main part of cognitive research and linguacultural concept as well. There is presented some famous scholars who have done valuable research in the anthropocentrism. Some conclusions have been made according to the article.

Keywords: anthropocentric paradigm, pragmatics, cognitive linguistics, concept, researchers, linguoculturalism, cognition, phenomenon, language personality.

ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING ANTROPOTSENTRIK TADQIQI MASALALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada asosan kognitiv lingvistika va lingvokulturologiyaga qaratilgan antropotsentrik paradigma aks ettirilgan. Shuningdek, kognitiv tadqiqotlar va lingvokulturologiya kontseptsiyasining asosiy qismi sifatidagi tushuncha ham tahlil qilingan. Antropotsentrizm boʻyicha qimmatli tadqiqotlar olib borgan baʼzi mashhur olimlarning maʼlumotlari keltirilgan. Maqolaga muvofiq baʼzi xulosalar chiqarildi.

Kalit soʻzlar: antropotsentrik paradigma, pragmatika, kognitiv lingvistika, kontseptsiya, tadqiqotchilar, lingvokulturalizma, bilish, hodisa, til shaxsi.

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ АНТРОПОЦЕНТРИЧЕСКОГО ИЗУЧЕНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлена антропоцентрическая парадигма, которая в основном фокусируется на когнитивной лингвистике и лингвокультурологии. Также анализируется концепт как основная часть когнитивных исследований и лингвокультурологический концепт. выводы сделаны по статье.

Ключевые слова: антропоцентрическая парадигма, прагматика, когнитивная лингвистика, концепт, исследователи, лингвокультурализм, познание, феномен, языковая личность.

In Uzbek linguistics researches based on the anthropocentric paradigm started from the early years of the 21st century. These researches have been mainly carried out in the directions of general theoretical issues of sociolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, linguistic pragmatics, psycholinguistics and the anthropocentric paradigm. Professor Sh. S. Safarov describes the emergence of the anthropocentric paradigm as follows: "The system-structural paradigm is the "atomistic" of the comparative historical paradigm that arose before it, it took the way to eliminate the defects that arose as a result of being analyzed the language phenomena separately from each other. The main effect of System-structural direction is to prove that language is a systematic phenomenon. But it also turns out that these two paradigms have a common drawback. In these directions, the language was separated from its owner -speaker. This defect attempts at loss pragmatic and cognitive linguistics caused the creation of paradigms". At the same time, the anthropocentric approach to language is the most of these fields as an independent paradigm, embodying the latest achievements is strengthening its status more and more. According to recognition of many researchers cognitive linguistics and linguoculturalism are the leading directions of the anthropocentric paradigm. [1,408-409] Cognitive linguistics (linguistics) is the study of human thinking, consciousness, mental functions and it is closely related to cognitivism, whose research object is a specific system and signals that shape the way of thinking of people, the activity they do as well as knowledge and perception. Cognitive world of any person is determined by their mental actions and life experiences. In this regard, language is the main sign of the above. In linguoculturology, such scientists as N. D. Arutyunova, Z. Kh. Bizheva, A. V. Vezhbitskaya, S. G. Vorkachev, V. I. Karasik, V. A. Stepanova, V. N. Telia, G. V. Tokareva, R. M. Frumkina dedicated their works to the study of concepts. Researchers consider the concept as a mental unit that is formed in the mind of a person under the influence of many factors, for example, social environment, religion, culture, and etc [3,63]

According to a number of specialists, cognitive linguistics and linguistic culturology (linguaculturology) is progressing in the frame of the collection of single general cognitive sciences. The term of "Cognitive science" includes learning processes jointly, receiving them and reworking, saving and using, organizing structure of knowledge and collection. Furthermore, it arranges collection of a certain scientific thoughts, which is combined for forming the mental activity of these structures. Cognitive science is closely connected with mathematics, logic, philosophy, anthropology and linguistics. Linguaculturology is a complex scientific science direction appeared in the basis of inter reaction of linguistics and culturology. This direction investigates interconnection between culture and language, and researches

the language as a phenomenon of culture. It shows the observation of the world in the certain view by the cultural prism and by a certain nation's mind and culture.[4,36]

According to V. Telia, culture is described as a world-conception, world perception and world-comprehension of a people. (This statement does not certainly deny the material component of culture but only puts in focus its "ideal" / mental component, which is much more significant for lingual-cultural and lingualcognitive studies.) Therefore, lingua-culture is the verbalized culture, the culture externalized in signs of language. Hence, signs of language (in the linguistic sense of this term) are regarded as the substances for signs of culture. Culture itself is not; however, simply a body of knowledge but rather a framework in which people live their lives and communicate shared meanings with each other.[5,207-208] Regarding the benefits of learning about culture, attending the culture class has raised cultural awareness in ELT students concerning both native and target societies. Moreover, V.Vorobyov gave a comprehensive and standard definition of linguaculturology. In his opinion, it is complex scientific discipline studying interrelation and interaction of culture and language. While, S.A.Kosharnaya defined it as the scientific discipline studying process of comprehension and reflection in national language of elements of material and spiritual culture of the people. The analysis of these and other existing definitions of linguaculturology shows establishment of the following:

- The linguaculturology is closely connected with Linguistics and Cultural science and has synthesizing character;
- The linguaculturology focuses the main attention on the cultural facts which are explicit in language;
- The linguaculturology belongs to linguistic sciences therefore results of its theoretical generalizations can find practical use in the course of training of native and foreign language;

Hence, following thoughtful deliberation, we might draw a conclusion on the difference in approaches to the study of concepts:

- Today, cognitive linguistics has become the main field of anthropocentric paradigm and due to such uzbek scholars as S.Safarov, D.U.Ashurova, O'.Q.Yusupov, G'.M.Hoshimov, M.Hakimov the cognitive and pragmatic linguistics reached to much clarification as they have done several research in these domain opening the way for further another research.

REFERENCES:

1. Akhunova, N. (2021). Comparative analysis of Indicative, Imperative and Subjunctive Moods in English and Uzbek languages. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(2), 25-30.
2. Nozima, O. (2022). Teaching English language to uzbek students of mathematics field, pedagogical analyses and considerations. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(02), 436-441.
3. Kizi, Z. K. (2022). " IN THE VORTEX OF HARDSHIPS" NOVEL. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 21, 87-89.
4. «SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS» Scientific Journal ISSN: 2181-1601 Volume: 1, ISSUE: 5 CONCEPT AND UNIVERSAL NATURE OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS Nursulton Zamon ugli Shaykhislamov Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent Region, pp.408-409
5. Kubryakova, E. S. *Voprosy yazykoznaniiya*, 1994, No. 4, pp. 34–38.
6. Scientific-methodological electronic journal “Foreign Languages in Uzbekistan”, 2021, No 6 (41), 60-68 <https://journal.fledu.uz> ISSN: 2181-8215 (online)
7. UNDERLYING DIFFERENCES BETWEEN COGNITIVE AND LINGUOCULTURAL CONCEPTS IN THE FIELD OF COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS AND LINGUOCULTUROLOGY Sanam Rustamovna FAYZIEVA Master’s degree student Faculty of Linguistics (English language) Uzbekistan State World Languages University Tashkent, Uzbekistan, pp.63
8. Zumratkhon SHUKUROVA Senior Teacher Uzbekistan State World Languages University LINGUACULTUROLOGY AS A MODERN BRANCH OF GENERAL LINGUISTICS www.fledu.uz, pp.36
9. Телия В. Н. Лингвокультурология – ключ к новой реальности феномена воспроизводимости нескольких словных образований // Язык. Культура. Общение: Сборник научных трудов в честь юбилея С.Г. Тер-Минасовой. – М.: Гнозис, 2008. – С. 207–216
10. "TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO UZBEK STUDENTS OF MATHEMATICS FIELD, PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSES AND CONSIDERATIONS "article by N.Ohunova 2022